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At the Crossroads of Civilizations:
STADESCA, A Pact of Stability,
Development and Security
for Central Asia

Political Situation in Afghanistan

China's Emerging Role and the Implications
for Kazakhstan

Kazakhstan's Transit Potential:
Key Components Assessment

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ABOUT ETHNIC-POLITICAL ASPECTS OF CENTRAL ASIAN STABILITY¹

Interethnic relations, especially along Uzbekistan's borders, are one of the main factors, which affect the regional security of Central Asia. The multiethnic character of Uzbekistan's provinces means that the possibility of an interethnic crisis, arising from territorial claims and water problems, is always present².

Geographically Central Asia is in the middle of Eurasia, meaning that the interests of many countries intersect here. In this situation, the republics of Central Asia are not the only governments whose policies affect the region's security. Instead, the regional stability of Central Asia depends on a variety of *internal and external* factors. Internal factors can be summarized as follows: interethnic relations; territorial pretensions; the dense population of certain parts of the region; water problems; the religious factor.

External factors may have a religious, cultural or economic essence. Some countries, in attempting to promote their interests in the region, rely on cultural or religious ties. Other countries emphasize economic relations. In all cases, however, economic issues remain the main and definitive factor.

When speaking of internal factors, it is necessary to state that many of these issues have a historical origin. For example: all of the territorial pretensions appeared after nation-state delineation in the first quarter of the 20th century. In order to rule more easily, the Bolsheviks divided the region into five separate countries. According to the famous orientalist V.V.Bartold, although some of the local ethnic groups were not ready to build their own state, the Bolsheviks nonetheless made them the titular basis of new nation-states³. In theory all of these republics had sovereignty, with a constitution and a name, but in reality they were ruled by the Communist Party from Moscow.

The process of drawing border between these republics was also problematic. During delimitation some of the region's ethnic groups remained outside the administrative borders of their alleged "homeland". This means that the ethnic map of the region does not correspond to its political map. Some researchers, in their discussion of regional problems in Central Asia, say that the current situation could take on a new form at any time in response to the foreign policy of Great Powers. These researchers emphasize the region's water, border and interethnic questions. Some of them also raise the Caspian question, a foreign policy issue not only for the states of Kazakhstan, Russia, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan and Iran, who border the sea, but also for distant countries which have interests in the region.

Although the conflicts over ethnic meaning among the ethnic groups of Central Asia are often ignored by local media providers, a number of articles are published in international media sources that discuss territorial claims between the republics as well as interethnic problems in the region. The consensus of public opinion in Central Asia is that such publications inflame already negative attitudes between the region's ethnic groups. Common to these articles are reductive analysis and judgements on the part of the journalists. Though the ethnic question is approached from many

¹ *This article is published in the Journal of Central Asia's Affairs, # 1, 2006, KISI Kazakhstan.*

² Жалилов А. Исследование этнотерриториальных аспектов стабильности в Центральной Азии. // Международные отношения. № 2. 2002. С. 33-40.

³ Архив АН СССР, ф. 68. Бартольд Василий Владимирович, оп.1, ед.хр. 85. (Archive of Academy of Science, f. 68. Bartold V.V., op.1. yed. xr.85)

different angles, it is generally done without regard for scientific validity or objectivity. It can be concluded, that while the issues of interethnic relations or territorial conflict are analysed from different sides, many of these analysis are provocative articles that contribute to the destabilization of the region. It can also be affirmed, that the interethnic question has important significance in the maintenance of regional stability and therefore requires in-depth study and impartial assessment.

Regional problems do not occur in and of themselves; their primary causes always stem from history. To understand the essence of the real ethnic-political card of Central Asia, it is necessary to address the historical and geographical distribution of Central Asia's ethnic groups and study it from the period of nation-state delimitation, which was conducted in the 1920's. Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, new causes of chaos in the region have appeared and are rising.

The communists skilfully used a "divide and conquer" strategy of separating the locals of different nationalities in the hasty formation of national republics. V.Volkov, the Director of the Institute of Slavonian and Balkan Studies at the Russian Academy of Sciences, agrees that during nation-state delimitation many mistakes were made and that they especially appeared in Russia and Central Asia⁴. The German scientist G.Diter accedes to this thought and in the article "The Regional integration in Central Asia", he asserts that the interethnic problem is one of the main questions affecting regional security in Central Asia⁵. In his judgement the present inter-republic borders do not grow from the historical development of the republics, but were created by hasty delimitation. Delimitation lasted ten years and in this process many national leaders perished in an unsuccessful struggle to preserve Central Asia as a unified state. The above-stated publications, which have increased since independence, in many respects express the interests of external political forces, which attempt to saddle local ethnic groups with an eternally insoluble problem.

Uzbekistan is a unique country, which shares borders with all of the former Soviet Republics. In almost all of the border areas the local ethnic groups of Central Asia live together. They have the same history, and similar cultures, religion and language. Nowadays the term Central Asia has only geographical meaning, but before the October Revolution there was governmental unity as well. While there were multiple different local power centers, located in such historical cores as Tashkent and Samarakand, the Bukharan Emirate had become the region's de facto leader as far as foreign relations were concerned. To rule more easily the Bolsheviks divided the region into five separate republics⁶. This process, i.e. the delimitation, was conducted without regard for local traditions, religion, culture etc⁷. After the completion of delimitation, some ethnic groups were deprived of their historical lands. In some places the same ethnic group now lives on both sides of the border, or a number of different ethnic groups live in one area. For instance, Osh is in Kyrgystan, Khodjent is in Tajikistan, both border provinces of present day Uzbekistan⁸. In certain cases, the border between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan will run right through the middle of a family's living room. One family had their house in Uzbekistan, and their backyard in Kazakhstan. The family's toilet was in an outbuilding in the backyard, and when people used it they would say "I'm going abroad".

Since the collapse of the unified Soviet economic system, a number of problems related to ethnic relations, ethnic policy and minority rights, and custom systems have begun to appear. In spite of generally good relations between the Central Asian republics some of these problems can

⁴ Волков В. Этнократия - непредвиденный феномен посттоталитарного мира // Полис, N 2, 1993, с. 42. (V.Volkov. Ethnocracy: the unpredictable phenomenon of the post-totalitarian world // POLIS, # 2, 1993, s 42)

⁵ Гериберт Дитер. Региональная интеграция в Центральной Азии. – Берлин: ГФМР, 1995. (in Russian)

⁶ Масов Р. История топорного разделения. Душанбе, 1991, с. 5.

⁷ Магидович И. Административное деление. Население. Материалы по районированию Средне Азии. Кн. 1. Территория и население Бухары и Хорезма. Часть 1. Хорезм, Ташкент, 1926, с. 174.

⁸ Ф.Толіпов. Границы государства и границы самоопределения: политика безопасности и политика национализма в Центральной Азии. <http://ftolipov.freenet.uz/borders.htm>

occasionally become very intense. Politicians assert that the Fergana valley is the basic point of regional stability, where there are literally explosive ethnic contradictions. Thorough research of these problems is needed to analyze the issue. Today these questions are widely studied at scientific and political centres not only in Central Asia, but in many foreign countries as well.

As a result of the complex political processes of the last 10 years, precise regional problems have formed, and the great necessity of protecting the republics from real threats is felt. According to local (Central Asian) scholars, these fears do not come from speculative reasoning. The last few years have brought to the forefront several problems which were initiated from the outside but which find a real embodiment in the region. Accordingly, the present situation requires steadfast study of the state interests of the republics. Such a study would examine what the interests of the five republics are, and attempt to ascertain what factors have the potential to harm or help the republics in their pursuit of these interests. It would also look outside the region, and attempt to discover what foreign powers—for example, China, the United States, and Russia—have interests in Central Asia, and how these varying interests might be in conflict with each other. Lastly, it would examine not only how foreign powers exploit cleavages within Central Asia when in pursuit of their policy goals, but also how Central Asian leaders attempt to promote their own interests by taking advantage of policy conflicts between the great powers. Today, in light of the short geopolitical history of Central Asia after independence—which has nonetheless included political turmoil in the south of Kyrgyzstan, in Tajikistan and in Afghanistan—a sober estimation of ethnic-political and territorial problems is necessary.

The geopolitical characteristic of the region

Before proceeding to analysis of these issues, it is necessary to outline the geopolitical characteristics of the region inside "Greater Central Asia". It will be useful, first to understand the reason for the transformation of ethnic questions into political questions, and second to give partial answers to the question of the actualisation and revival of ethnic-political factors in our region.

Central Asia is the centre of the Eurasian continent, a huge territory with more than 50 million people. The region borders such Great Powers as Russia and China, as well as increasingly influential countries like India and Iran. The length of the external borders of the republics of Central Asia is more than 20,000 km. The southern parts of the region are the most complex from the point of view of geopolitical processes, which in light of recent events (Osh events, Kokand, Parkent events, continuing illegal trade in border areas) play a determining role for strategic balance not only inside the region, but also worldwide on all continents. Despite the destruction of the international terrorist bases in neighbouring Afghanistan, the possibility of threats to the region intensifying is still present.

On the other hand, enormous stocks of natural resources, along with favourable geographical and climatic conditions, open colossal economic opportunities. For example, Kazakhstan has proven oil reserves of 16 billion barrels and might have an additional 30 billion barrels both onshore and under its portion of the Caspian seabed. Significant oil reserves have prompted the world's oil majors to play an active role in the development of Kazakhstan's oil reserves.⁹ The region is also a potential new market for multinational corporations.

Z.Brzezinsky writes that from 1993 to 2015 the volume of consumption of energy resources in the world will grow by 50 %; this creates a huge pressure to study and open new energy sources. In this connection, the Central Asian region -- rich in energy resources and at the same time unstable in its ethnic-territorial situation -- could become a stage for a global antagonism.¹⁰ Briefly,

⁹ Author: BISNIS Representative in Kazakhstan September 2001
<http://www.bisnis.doc.gov/bisnis/isa/010917kazoilgas.htm>

¹⁰ Збигнев Бжежинский. Великая шахматная доска. Москва. "Международные отношения" 2000. С 149 – 163.

Central Asia on many levels is attractive, and so Great Powers will try to develop their geopolitical and economic interests in the region.

From a geographical perspective Central Asia is on the "line of scrimmage" of a geopolitical game, in which the two most powerful players are the USA and Russia. The story is of an antagonism between "core" and "periphery", which has continued on the whole Eurasian continent for centuries. The interest of USA, China, India, Pakistan, Iran and Turkey in the character and direction of geopolitical processes in Central Asia also grows. Some foreign powers from time to time try to play religious and/or "ethnic-political card" of Central Asia. Hence, the outbreak of geopolitical problems in Central Asia (in this case the possibility of an ethnic-political crisis), is only one part of that long antagonism, and therefore, the creation of a crisis depends on the strengthening of struggle or a change in the strategy and tactics of the parties.

The ethnic features of Central Asia require special attention and in-depth analysis. Ethnic-political tensions are explained by discrepancies between the ethnic map of the region and the political map. Along all of the region's borders, portions of the titular ethnic group of one republic will live on land belonging to a neighboring republic, and the republics use this fact as a basis for making territorial claims to one another's land. It is so in the southern territories of Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, and also in the eastern and northern provinces of Tajikistan. In Kazakhstan more than 50 % of the population is Slavic or other non-Kazakh nationalities. Furthermore, delimitation between republics is not yet finished, and it has disputable moments. The complexity of the realization of delimitation in the region is explained by the inaccessibility of some boundary sites between republics. Delimitation between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, and also between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan has been finished successfully. However some disagreements could still arise at specification of borders in mountainous districts between Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan.

Usually many questions between the republics of Central Asia are discussed and solved by intergovernmental commissions. Questions of external-political or even of military and technical character are gradually being solved by such commissions. There has been little public discussion of these issues in Central Asian media sources so most Central Asian citizens get their information on these issues from media sources based in Russia. The strengthening of external factors means that increased attention is being paid to these interethnic questions. This is the explanation for the increase of articles in foreign mass media, in which interethnic problems are discussed. But for valid conclusions on the ethnic-political question it is necessary to address the historical ethnic map of the region. This article is an attempt to present such a scholarly view point on the ethnic-political question, and hopefully thereby to counter some of the ill-thought out views which have become all too common in articles on this topic.

An ethnic characterization of Central Asia

The multi-national state is a not-uncommon variety of societies, but the strengthening of geopolitical processes in 20th century has turned it into a strong political implement. The phenomenon is sometimes used as a tool with which to pressure or ethnically polarize a country or a region, with the purpose of realizing a particular geopolitical or economic plan.

In multiethnic societies there are disputes on ethnic grounds as to which side ostensibly is in the right. Should conflict occur, both sides will attempt to claim the moral high-ground, perhaps by claiming that the other side was responsible for precipitating the clash, or perhaps by claiming that they have a historical claim to a disputed territory. In other words, in such regions leaders will invoke various historical or territorial factors when pursuing national ambitions.

In the opinion of Central Asian experts', the region has grounds for ethnic-political and territorial problems, which could result from the following factors:

- First, the complex ethnic structure of the frontier areas;
- Second, friction between the republics based on the official policies towards each other;

- Third, internal government policies that benefit one ethnic group at the expense of others¹¹;
- Fourth, complex arrangements between the republics for the distribution of water resources of the Syrdarya and Amudarya basins¹²;
- Fifth, struggle between Great Powers for the rich natural resources of the region in consequence of a possible increase in global energy demand.

A major aspect of Central Asian security is the maintenance of interethnic consent in the republics in the face of these factors. All of the republics are multinational, with the titular nation of the republic living alongside other Central Asian ethnic groups as well as a Russian-speaking population and other ethnic groups. Generally the principles of consent and being good neighbours that provide for the development of bilateral relations between the republics also characterize local interethnic relations in the region.

The multi-national demography of the Central Asian countries dates from the first quarter of the 20th century, and the history of resettlement of ethnic minorities to the region is well known. For example, almost all the Russian-speaking population in the republics arrived during the period of the Soviet authority, either for the establishment Bolshevik authority or under the pretext of developing a national economy or by deportation. Thus, during the so-called poly-ethnization process under Soviet authority, the national structure of the region increased to 110 ethnic groups.

It is necessary to note that the tolerance of Central Asian ethnic groups allowed for the gradual increase in the number of minorities in the republics. Additionally, the poly-ethnicity of Central Asia was in due course perceived as cultural richness, and this phenomenon in itself did not threaten security and stability inside the separate countries or the region as a whole.

However, geopolitical processes at the end of the 20th century—in particular, competition over potential energy resources-- have changed the character of the antagonism among the Great Powers. On leaving the frameworks of normal political processes this antagonism has transformed even ethnic cultural factors into political threats. Accordingly, the investigated ethnic-political phenomenon in Central Asia could become menacing with the strengthening influence of external factors.

Uzbeks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Tajiks, Karakalpaks and Uygurs have lived in Central Asia from ancient times, and they have shared ethnic-cultural and religious roots. The affinity of ethnic groups is expressed in various aspects of their lives. For example, the Kazakhs, Kyrgyz and Karakalpaks (and partially Uzbeks) have not only linguistic similarity, but also a similar lifestyle and economy. Tajik, however, is included in the Persian language group. While there is small number of Shiite Tajiks, the majority are Sunni, as are the Uzbeks. Notwithstanding the existence of distinct languages, Uzbeks and Tajiks are extremely similar on most ethnic-cultural characteristics.

It is very well known that until the creation of national republics for the above named ethnic groups, the existence of distinct ethnic - cultural features and ethnic names never equated state isolation or separation. Before occupation by Imperial Russia, the state devices in Central Asia were formed on territorial and dynastic principles, which were organized around such historical centres as Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand, Samarkand, and Tashkent.

To a question about nationality, the people responded with their religious belief - "muslim", or by naming a place of residence – Kokand, Dashhavuz, Shimkent, Osh etc.¹³ The territorial location of ethnic groups had no serious significance in public administration. In other words, if ethnic features mattered, it was expressed through management of regions and/or distribution of administrative positions; it did not reflect a separatist mood in the modern sense. The various local

¹¹ Демократизм, национализм и регионализм в Центральной Азии. Центральная Азия и Кавказ, № 4, 2000

¹² Усубалиев Е., Усубалиев Э. Проблемы территориального урегулирования и распределения водно-энергетических ресурсов в Центральной Азии. - Центральная Азия и Кавказ, №1, 2002. See: Гулямов Я.Г. История орошения Хорезма. Ташкент, 1957, с. 313.

¹³ See also, В. В. Бартольд. Сочинения. Т. 6. М., 1966, с. 15—72. (V.V. Bartold. Collected works. V 6, M., 1966)

ethnic groups lived on the plains, in urban settlements, and also in mountain districts. The Kazakhs, Kararalpaks and Turkmen usually lived in flat areas of the region and had pastoral nomadic lifestyles. The Uzbeks and some of the Tajiks lived in the valleys, in urban settlements and in mountain districts of Central Asia. The Kyrgyz were also nomadic and lived at the foothills of the Tien Shan mountain range.

Ethnic - political and territorial problems began to arise after Sherbin's expedition in the 1920's and followed the formation of national republics. To understand the true reasons of the discrepancy between the present ethnic and political maps of the region, it is necessary first of all to look at the historical location of ethnic groups up to the first quarter of the 20th century.¹⁴

It is necessary to recognize, that in the world there exist more than 1600 ethnic groups, but only 300 states. This means that most ethnic groups do not have the opportunity to create their own state under their own name. Living on the territory of another state, they belong to an ethnic minority, which may require special policy. The various ethnic groups of the region have been living together in these border provinces for centuries, the resulting complex ethnic map is a fact that ethnic policies must account for but cannot reverse. Many of them, in spite of living in their historical territory, remained outside of their titular state's border after the 1920's delimitation, and became national minorities in neighbouring countries. This is a convenient trump for certain forces, which today frequently play the ethnic-political card in Central Asia. However, a deep analysis of the historical formation of the ethnic map and the contemporary location of the ethnic groups in the region makes us convinced that such territorial location of ethnic groups is the result of the historical development of the region and by itself would not have become the factor of destabilization. The basic reasons for possible ethnic-territorial problems rest on the artificial nation-state delimitation of a uniform Central Asia.

All of the titular ethnic groups of the region live on the territories of their historical homelands, and such territorial location of ethnic groups expresses a natural historical ethnic-map of the region. Culture and the methods of managing local ethnic groups were formed through the centuries strictly under the influence of natural-climatic conditions. Hence, a pastoral nomadic lifestyle and the appropriate methods of management are inherent to the ethnic groups of the flat areas and north-eastern foothill territories. The urban population basically lived in the river valleys of the region and their life, culture and economy were formed under the influence of corresponding factors. Thus, before the realization of national-state delimitation, i.e. before the 1920's, questions of territorial division among local ethnic groups were not essential. The questions connected to the ethnic map of the region have an underlying politically motivation, which originated from external sources. Nowadays, Central Asia is referred to as a place of boiling ethnic contradictions and is compared to the Balkans.

For the formation of final conclusions it is necessary to address the demographic parameters and location of the ethnic groups on the contemporary political map of region. Of the five states of Central Asia, only Uzbekistan has a state border with all of the other countries of the region. Hence, the ethnic structure and interethnic relations of border areas of this republic have especial importance for regional stability.

"The local national minorities"

The so-called local national minorities of Uzbekistan usually live in the republics border provinces. The word "national minority" designates all ethnic groups other than the titular ethnic group of the country. It is necessary to note that the national minorities of a specific state cannot be the titular nation of that state; however they can be a local ethnic group of the region, which may include several historically and culturally connected states. Thus, one nation state's titular ethnic group will be part of the national minority in a neighbouring state. In the case of Central Asia, the national minorities are all local ethnic groups of the Central Asian republics, who happen to live on

¹⁴ About results of national state delimitation in the region: Xidoyatov G.A. Security and cooperation in Central Asia: problems, searches, decision. // International Relations. # 3. 2001. pp. 53-65.

each other's territory. Certainly, the national minorities of this region are very different from such diasporas as, for example, exist in the USA¹⁵.

In other words, basic parts of the local national minorities of Central Asian border territories are not deportants. They are instead the historical inhabitants of the ground upon which they live today. They did not emigrate to a republic foreign to them; rather, state boundaries were drawn around them which artificially turned them into a 'minority.' A dominant part of all ethnic minorities of Central Asia live in districts bordering their "homeland". For example, ethnic Uzbeks as a minority are located in the provinces adjacent to Uzbekistan of all the countries around our republic. There are also Kazakhs in Uzbekistan, Tajiks in Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzs in Tajikistan etc. Thus, it would be desirable once again to mention the national-state delimitation in the beginning of the last century that resulted in the artificial formation of so-called "national minorities" in the region¹⁶.

It is necessary to note of the present interethnic situation in the region, that the attitude of local ethnic groups does not warrant the application to them of the alien word "national minority" in the genuine meaning of this concept. A deep scientific approach explains the given phenomenon a little differently: the term "the national minority" does not reflect the real attitude of local ethnic groups of Central Asia. Uzbeks living in Tajikistan do not necessarily view themselves as constituting a "minority" population distinct from the mass of "Tajik" citizens—the same can be said of Kazakhs in Uzbekistan, Uzbeks in Kyrgyzstan, etc. Proceeding from this, the idea of "national minority" in Central Asia is a relative phenomenon. Such relativity arises first of all, from the geographical location of ethnic groups, i.e. their continued inhabitation of their historical motherland. Second, the transparency of borders allows ethnic groups to maintain close relationships with relatives on the other side, and thus automatically pushes the concept "of state border" to a place of secondary importance.

Third, all the ethnic groups have in common participation in economic activities, history and traditional culture and lifestyle, which are connected and are crossed in daily life. Such similarity does not allow an ethnic group to be alienated from the public unity of the region where they live. Public unity is as we know a rather important factor in the political and cultural life of the region. The main traditional activities, such as weddings, funeral, xashars¹⁷ etc. are carried out with common effort, despite ethnic differences. Such traditions draw together and unite the various frontier peoples. This can be observed in any area where the Uzbek, Kazakh, Tajik, Turkmen and Kyrgyz people live together. Psychological loyalty to one another and tolerance have allowed for the peaceful preservation of ethnic differences. These ideas prevented infringements on the ethnic originality of another people. In this process, there occurred not only preservation of ethnic identification, but also ties between ethnic groups. In a broad sense this is explained by a generality of not only mentality, culture, history, geography, but also of economic bases and preconditions. These are the elements and bases that characterize the relativity of the "national minority" idea in Central Asia.

¹⁵ Жалилов А. Диаспоралар (этно-сиёсий ходисанинг назарий тахлили) Халқаро муносабатлар. // # 4. 2001.

¹⁶ Хакимов М.Х. Партия и советская национальная государственность. Руководство КПСС созданием и развитием советской государственности народов Средней Азии и Казахстана. Ташкент, 1980, с. 221-222.

¹⁷ Xashar is widespread in Central Asia traditional working style. Young men of the villages are carrying out all the difficult works together. The main characteristic of the xashar is effective physical collective work.

Preserving the traditional amicability of Central Asian inter-ethnic relations is the central challenge for Central Asian republics who wish to retain peaceful relationships in the region. Analysis of ethnic and geographical characteristics and of present and future demographic parameters reveals the real complexity of the ethnic-territorial questions in Central Asia. Analysis of the above-stated issues makes it possible to reach the following conclusions about regional ethnic-political stability:

1. The ethnically mixed population of border territories determines the specificity and complexity of an interethnic situation.

2. Ethnic-territorial problems which from time to time are played out in the region, often occur in response to a change in the tactics and strategy of external forces. Hence, the urgency of interethnic questions is kept and reflected in mutual relation of republics. In order to preserve their stability and security, the Central Asian states should:

- Not allow external forces to use the multiethnic nature of border territories as a tool when in pursuit of their foreign policy goals;

- Carry out national policies that conform to the standards of multiethnic communities and organize educational and informational campaigns about these principles;

- Protect the citizens from the destructive propagation of national violence;

- Complete the delimitation of state borders, which will also promote ethnic and territorial stability;

- Ensure simpler rules for the custom services, in order to preserve close cross-border interethnic relations;

- Ensure the safety of transit vehicles.

Despite the realization of similar measures the socio-economic difficulties caused by market interests can promote forces which destabilize the political situation in the region. Such efforts are expressed mainly in attempts to bring out disagreements between local ethnic groups: this is reflected in the distortion of historical facts, historical development of culture and modern political events etc. They can be especially observed in the publications of foreign authors. For the region to achieve stability in interethnic relations, the republics' must counter these destabilizing factors by developing and implementing calm and carefully-considered policies aimed at the promotion of peaceful interethnic relations, and especially at the promotion of tolerance on the part of a republic's titular ethnic group.